

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT

Breeding methods

Agronomic performance and genetic correlations of rice mutants

M. L. H. Kaul and Neelangini, Botany Department, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra 132119, India

By using different mutagen doses, we isolated five mutants in rice varieties IR8, Jhona, and Basmati (Table 1). Both mutants of IR8 (IRm₁ and IRm₆) are early and fine-grained, with higher seed protein content. Both mutants of Jhona (Jm₁ and Jm₄) are shorter and yield higher than their parent. Jm₄ has higher grain number and grain yield than Jm₁. Basmati mutant Bm₁ has shorter duration and is shorter and has finer grains, with higher grain number, protein content, and seed yield, than Basmati.

Although the genetic parameters phenotypic and genotypic coefficients of variation, heritability, genetic advance, and expected genetic advance were not different in the mutants, significant differences in certain genetic correlations were exhibited (Table 2). Grain yield became negatively correlated with grain fineness and positively correlated with grain weight; these correlations are not significant in the parent varieties. Grain fineness in the parent varieties is not correlated with grain weight and grain

Table 1. Performance of rice mutants and their parent lines. Kurukshetra University, India.

Parent and mutant	Mutagen and dosage ^a	Shoot height ^a (cm)	Maturity ^a (d)	Fertile grain ^a (no.)	Grain fineness ^a	Grain yield ^a (g/plant)	Seed protein content ^b (%)
IR8	—	88.1	153	753	2.39	21.1	7.6
IRm ₁	EMS 1.5%	110.5	128	903	2.84	22.7	8.2
IRm ₆	EMS 1.5%	88.7	119	982	2.66	22.5	8.7
	LSD (0.05)	3.9	5.7	19.9	0.13	1.2	0.2
Jhona	—	133.5	127	1012	2.29	20.4	7.8
Jm ₁	EMS 1.5%	122.9	125	1081	2.45	22.9	7.9
Jm ₄	r-rays 20 kR + 1% EMS	124.5	123	1130	2.47	24.1	7.7
	LSD (0.05)	5.8	7.4	28.31	0.09	1.6	0.15
Basmati	—	151.8	152	789	3.63	15.9	7.6
Bm ₁	EMS 0.5%	140.7	142	878	3.60	17.4	8.4
	LSD (0.05)	5.2	4.5	21.6	0.08	0.1	0.1

^aMean of 360 observations (40 plants × 3 replications × 3 generations). ^bMean of 90 observations (10 plants × 3 replications × 3 generations).

Table 2. Correlations^a of genetic traits between parent varieties and mutant lines. Kurukshetra University, India.

Trait		GY	GF	GW	GN	SH
Grain yield (GY)	Parent	ns	ns	ns	+	ns
	Mutant	ns	—	+	+	ns
Grain fineness (GF)	Parent	.05	ns	ns	ns	+
	Mutant	-.29*	ns	—	—	+
Grain weight (GW)	Parent	.15	-.49	ns	—	ns
	Mutant	.29*	-.25*	ns	—	—
Grain number (GN)	Parent	.70*	.39	-.59*	ns	ns
	Mutant	.22*	-.14*	-.23*	ns	ns
Shoot height (SH)	Parent	-.02	.39*	-.15	.09	ns
	Mutant	.23	.31*	-.28*	.21	ns

^ans = not significant, + = positive, - = negative, * = significant value, SE > \bar{n} .

number; in the mutants, these correlations are negative and significant. Shoot height in the mutants is negatively correlated with grain weight; in the parents, this correlation is not

significant.

Whether these represent mutational changes or chance changes needs to be determined, using a large sample of mutant types. □

Hybrid rice heterosis in Tamil Nadu

M. Rangaswamy and K. Natarajamoorthy, School of Genetics, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003, India

We studied 38 F₁s involving Zhen Shan 97A and Er-jiu-Nan 1A as the female

parents during 1985 dry season. All combinations had high standard heterosis and heterobeltiosis for tiller numbers (see table).

High tiller numbers were reflected in straw yield, with standard heterosis as high as 134% and heterobeltiosis as high as 112%. Standard heterosis for grain yield was only 8%, because of heterosis

for spikelet sterility as high as 226% compared to the standard variety and 909% compared to the pollen parents.

Heterosis for tiller number gives scope for improving hybrid seed fertility by selecting restorers for genetic constitution and CMS lines for cytoplasmic content. □